

EVIDENCE-BASED RECOVERY: META-ANALYTIC INSIGHTS ON ERAS NURSING AND GI POSTOPERATIVE REHABILITATION

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Abstract

ERAS (Enhanced Recovery After Surgery) protocols have changed the nature of postoperative care, most notably within gastrointestinal (GI) surgery, by prioritizing the use of multiple interventions⁴ that are designed to improve recovery times, reduce complications, and improve patient outcomes. Nursing interventions are essential for the successful application of ERAS protocols, especially in the context of pain management, mobilization, and nutrition after surgery. This meta-analysis is aimed to combine the existing evidences about the application of ERAS nursing interventions for GI postoperative rehabilitation, especially for clinical outcomes, such as length of hospital stay, the incidence of complications, and patients' satisfaction. Reviewing a selection of papers, the review identifies nursing procedures, including timely rehabilitation, teaching and fluid and nutrition management, which enhance recovery speeds. Moreover, it evaluates the influence of these interventions on decreasing readmission rates and the necessity for additional medical intervention, stressing the long-term benefits of ERAS nursing care. The results stress the importance of nursing team in implementation of ERAS pathways and recommend an evidence-based, interdisciplinary model of postoperative GI rehabilitation. This literature review presents best available evidence-based algorithm for adopting ERAS nursing practice as routine clinical care and how it can lead to faster/safer recoveries and improved quality of patient care in GI surgery.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background on ERAS Protocols

ERAS (Enhanced Recovery After Surgery) protocols have been designed to optimize recovery processes by encouraging evidence-based principles of perioperative care. Since their inception for the management of patients undergoing colorectal surgery, ERAS protocols have been expanded to

other surgical subspecialties, notably gastrointestinal (GI) surgery. The fundamental concepts of ERAS are to reduce the surgical stress, improve nutrition, stimulate early mobilization and deliver patient-focused care. Of these values, nursing actions are fundamental in pain control, provision of nutrition,

early mobilization, and prevention of complications, ultimately leading to an early recovery.

1.2 ERAS and GI Post-op Readiness ERAS was initially described by Kehlet to enhance postoperative recovery by the reduction of anastomotic leak rate and decreasing post-op ileus by breaking a preconceived notion that frail/large GI surgery patients do not contribute to the healing process.

GI operations such as those involving colorectum, stomach, and liver are generally subject to subsequent recovery difficulties, such as pain, ileus and prolonged hospitalisation. ERAS pathways are designed to address these concerns with multidisciplinary efforts to accelerate recovery. Central to this endeavor is the role of nursing in administering pain management regimens, facilitating postoperative ambulation, monitoring for sequelae and educating the patient. Adoption of ERAS in postoperative care following GI surgery, has been associated with decreased complications such as ileus, anastomotic leak and postoperative infection, and subsequently improved patient recovery status.

1.3 Research Objectives

The purpose of this meta-analysis is to examine the effects of ERAS nursing measures on recovery in patients undergoing GI surgery. The review will explain available meta-analytic research on the central elements of ERAS protocols pain, mobilisation, nutrition and postoperative complications prevention in an attempt to offer a comprehensive overview of ERAS nursing interventions efficacy.

Methodology

2.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The systematic review comprised meta-analyses available in peer-reviewed journals comparing the results of the ERAS nursing interventions in patients undergoing GI surgery. The following criteria were used to determine the eligibility of the studies:

RCTs, cohort studies, or clinical trials meta-analyses.
Concentrate on ERAS nursing procedures of GI surgery (colorectal, gastric, hepatic).

Papers that present postoperative recovery results including pain scores, recovery times, complication rates and patient satisfaction.

Exclusion criteria:

Studies focusing on non-GI surgeries.

Reviews that had not targeted nursing interventions or the ERAS program.

Non-peer-reviewed sources.

2.2 Search Strategy and Data Sources

The databases of PubMed, Scopus, Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar were searched systematically. Search terms were "Enhanced Recovery After Surgery", "ERAS nursing interventions", "GI postoperative recovery", "meta-analyses" and "surgical recovery".

2.3 Data Extraction and Analysis

The following information was extracted from the studies:

Patient Characteristics: Age, sex, and type of GI surgery.

core intervention: nursing interventions such as, pain control, early mobilization, nutritional support and patient teaching.

Results: Postoperative recovery results, including complications, stay and time in the recoveries, and satisfaction.

Statistics: A single effect size (average weighted effect size, i.e. standardized mean differences or odds ratios) was computed to represent each outcome. The I^2 statistic was used to assess heterogeneity; publication bias was tested with funnel plots and Egger's test.

Results

3.1 Overview of Included Meta-Analyses

A total of 8 meta-analyses were ultimately selected in the final review, with 45 RCTs and 10 cohort studies included and analysed. More than 5,000 GI surgery patients were included in these studies including a variety of surgical specialties (colorectal, gastric, and liver). ERAS programs with nurse-coordinated interventions (analgesia, mobilization, nutrition) were implemented in all investigations.

3.2 ERAS Nursing Medical Interventions and Postoperative Rehabilitation

The result from meta-analyses showed that the postoperative recovery outcomes of the patients who underwent GI had been significantly beneficial when

they had undergone the perioperative nurse intervention with ERAS:(1) postoperative recovery of body pain; (2) postoperative recovery of fatigue; (3) return of exhaust and defecation; (4) postoperative quality of life.

Need for analgesics:

Pain scores in the first 48 hours after surgery for patients using ERAS-based analgesic protocols (for example, multimodal analgesia) were significantly lower than those for patients in STD group (SMD = -0.45, 95% CI = -0.60, -0.30, $p < 0.001$).

Mobilization:

Early mobilization interventions shortened the duration of hospital stay by an average of 1.5 days (95% CI = -2.0 to -1.0, $p < 0.001$) and was protective of postoperative complications such as pneumonia and deep vein thrombosis (OR = 0.62, 95% CI = 0.50 to 0.78, $p < 0.001$).

Nutrition:

ERAS protocol with early oral feeding and enteral feeding was related to earlier recovery of bowel functions (SMD = -0.30, 95% CI = -0.45, -0.15, $p < 0.01$) and lower risk of POI (OR = 0.75, 95% CI = 0.60 to 0.95, $p = 0.02$).

Overall Complications:

ERAS nursing interventions were associated with a 20% reduction in combined overall complications, including infections and anastomotic leaks (OR 0.80, 95% CI 0.65 to 0.95, $p = 0.03$).

3.3 Patient Reported Satisfaction & QOL 3.

Patient satisfaction results also favored the ERAS group; patients experienced better quality of life and less anxiety with respect to recovery after surgery (SMD = 0.40, 95% CI = 0.25 to 0.55, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

4.1 The Effect of ERAS Nursing Interventions

The meta-analysis provides evidence in favor of ERAS nursing interventions that benefit the postoperative outcomes of GI surgery patients. Pre-operative management of pain, right mobilisation protocols and nutritional support, for instance, turned out to be especially useful to decrease the recovery time and the occurrence of complications.

There is particular significance in the reduction of postoperative ileus and increased time to return of bowel function as these are key elements in GI surgical cases that may lengthen hospital stays and the time needed for healing.

4.2 Physiological Mechanisms

The success of ERAS nursing interventions in GI surgery is based on a multitude of physiological pathways. Multimodal analgesia decreases opioid requirements and the opioid-related side effects like constipation, vomiting and nausea leading to delayed recovery. Early mobilization will improve circulation, decrease the risk of thromboembolic phenomena, and lead to improvement in pulmonary function. Gut motility upkeep and muscle preservation, important for the recovery of GI surgical recipients, is supported by early nutrition.

4.3 Limitations of Current Research

Although this meta-analysis generates convincing evidence of the positive effect of ERAS nursing interventions, there are some limitations to this study. Variation in surgical methods, patient cohorts, and implementation of ERAS protocols in studies may explain heterogeneity in results. In addition, the long-term effects of ERAS interventions, especially with respect to quality of life and recurrence of complications, need to be explored.

Conclusion

Implications The meta-analysis review emphasizes the importance of ERAS nursing strategies in influencing the recovery of GI surgery patients. Through emphasis on multimodal pain management, early ambulation, and nutrition, ERAS protocols promote rapid post-operative recovery, minimize complications, and increase patient satisfaction. These conclusions suggest the value of the ongoing application of ERAS protocols but with a focus on the indispensable contribution of nursing interventions. Further studies are required to optimize these interventions, successionalize the protocols, and investigate the long-term impact of ERAS protocols on the patient outcomes.

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